

CHLORAMINE-T AS VOLUMETRIC REAGENT : DETERMINATION OF ORGANIC DERIVATIVES OF HYDRAZINE

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In presence of hydrochloric acid chloramine-T solution has been used as a volumetric reagent for the determination of semicarbazide hydrochloride, benzal semicarbazone, *o*-nitro-, *m*-nitro-, *o*-hydroxy-, *p*-methoxy-, *p*-chloro-, and *o*-chloro-benzal semicarbazones, acetone semicarbazone, benzoylhydrazine, benzalazine, 4-phenylsemicarbazide hydrochloride, thiosemicarbazide, phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and β -formylphenylhydrazine.

In visual titrations iodine monochloride-chloroform was used as an indicator. In potentiometric titrations, platinum electrode was used as an oxidation-reduction electrode and it was coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. At equivalence point there is a sharp jump in potential in each titration.

Noll (*Chem. Ztg.*, 1924, **48**, 485) described the use of chloramine-T [$p\text{-CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{SO}_2\text{N}(\text{Na})\text{Cl}\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, M. W. 281.5] as an oxidising agent. In solution it behaves as a stable hypochlorite. The reagent is finding an increasing use in place of sodium hypochlorite. It has the advantage that its aqueous solution is stable in air and shows little deterioration over long periods, when kept in stoppered dark bottles; moreover, as alkali is absent there is no risk of the formation of chlorates which lead to side reactions.

Rupp (*Pharm. Zentr.*, 1925, **66**, 33) used chloramine-T for the determination of antimony and stannous tin. Tomicek and Sucharda (*Chem. Abst.*, 1932, **26**, 1210) used it as a reagent for the potentiometric determination of arsenic, antimony, stannous tin, ferrous iron, ferrocyanide and iodide, and for visual titrations of antimony and arsenic using methyl red as indicator. Komarovskii *et al.* (*J. Appl. Chem.*, USSR, 1933, **6**, 742; *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1946, **96**, 321) have shown that chloramine-T can be used as a volumetric reagent to replace the more expensive iodine and less stable hypochlorite in the estimation of ferrocyanide, hydrazine and hypophosphite. Singh and Rehman (this *Journal*, 1940, **17**, 170) used this reagent for the potentiometric determination of sodium nitrite, sodium bisulphite, hydrazine hydrochloride and potassium iodide.

Lee *et al.* (*Anal. Chem.*, 1948, **20**, 431) used chloramine-T in the quantitative estimation of various organic sulphides. Afanas'ev (*J. Phys. Chem.*, USSR, 1948, **22**, 499) studied the oxidation-reduction potential and the mechanism of oxidation with chloramine-T and used it for the volumetric estimation of various organic compounds using indigo carmine and methyl red as indicators.

Singh *et al.* (*Res. Bull. East Panjab Univ.*, 1953, **30**, 55) have used chloramine-T for the potentiometric estimation of vanillin, *p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, acetaldehyde, furfural, urea, oxalic acid, thiourea, glycerol and mannitol. Singh and Sood (*Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1955, **13**, 30) have further extended the use of chloramine-T for the estimation of potassium iodide, hydrazine sulphate, mercurous chloride, arsenious oxide, stannous chloride, tartar emetic, potassium thiocyanate and ferrous ammonium sulphate by a volumetric procedure using iodine monochloride as a catalyst and preoxidiser, and chloroform as indicator. Spacu and Teodorescu (*Bul. inst. Politch Bucuresti*, 1956, **18**, 47) have used chloramine-T for the indirect determination of isonicotinyldiazine.

In the present study chloramine-T has been used as an oxidant for the estimation of semicarbazide hydrochloride, benzal semicarbazone, and several substituted semicarbazones, benzoylhydrazine, benzalazine, 4-phenylsemicarbazide hydrochloride, thiosemicarbazide, phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and β -formylphenylhydrazine, using iodine monochloride-chloroform as indicator in visual titrations. Equivalence point was also determined potentiometrically in most of the titrations.

In hydrochloric acid medium each molecule of the organic derivative of hydrazine is quantitatively oxidised with chloramine-T by a four-electron change per hydrazino group:

EXPERIMENTAL

Chloramine-T was prepared according to Vogel ("Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", p. 822, 1948). The reagent was standardised by an iodometric method.

Iodine Monochloride Method (Visual Titrations).—A known amount of each substance was taken in a conical flask and water (~25 c.c.), HCl (conc., 15 c.c.), 0.02 M iodine monochloride (5 c.c.) and chloroform (5 c.c.) were added to it. The mixture was cooled to room temperature and titrated with a standard (0.05M) chloramine-T solution. The reagent was added from a burette until the solution, which was coloured with iodine, became pale yellow and chloroform layer acquired a purple colour due to iodine. The conical flask was stoppered and vigorously shaken during the titration. Addition of small volumes of chloramine-T was continued, shaking vigorously after each addition until the chloroform layer became light pale yellow due to the formation of iodine monochloride. The end-point was very sharp.

In these titrations the normality of the solution with respect to HCl was kept between 2.5N and 4.5N excepting in the cases of semicarbazide hydrochloride and 4-phenylsemicarbazide hydrochloride, where the acid normality was maintained between 0.7N and 1.0N. Several titrations were performed in each case. From the volume of the standard chloramine-T solution used, corresponding to the end-point in each titration, the amount of each substance was calculated. Some typical results are recorded in Table I.

Potentiometric Method.—A known amount of each substance was taken in a beaker, and water (40 c.c.) and sufficient HCl (conc.) were added to keep normality of the mixture with respect to the acid between 5.0N and 5.5N. One drop of 0.005M potassium iodide solution was added as a catalyst. The mixture was titrated potentiometrically with 0.05M chloramine-T solution.

FIG. 1

A platinum wire electrode, immersed in the solution to be titrated, was used as an oxidation-reduction electrode, and this was coupled with a saturated calomel electrode. The mixture was kept stirred with a mechanical stirrer during titration. Progress of the reaction was studied with a Mullard potentiometer. At equivalence point a sharp jump in potential was observed in each titration. A series of potentiometric titrations were performed with different amounts of each substance. The potentiometric titrations, one for each substance, are represented by curves A to I in Fig. 1.

From the volume of standard (0.05M) chloramine-T solution used, corresponding to the end-point in each titration, the amount of each substance was calculated. Some typical results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Organic derivatives of hydrazine.	Weight of the hydrazine derivative by			
	Iodine monochloride method.		Potentiometric method.	
	Taken.	Found.	Taken.	Found.
NH ₂ CONH.NH ₂ .HCl	0.0139 g.	0.0139 g.	0.0111 g.	0.0111 g.
	0.0418	0.0417	0.0277	0.0277
C ₆ H ₅ CH:N.NHCONH ₂	0.0204	0.0204	0.0208	0.0208
	0.0617	0.0615	0.0492	0.0491
o-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH:N.NHCONH ₂	0.0218	0.0218	0.0260	0.0260
	0.0531	0.0529	0.0789	0.0791
p-ClC ₆ H ₄ CH:N.NHCONH ₂	0.0251	0.0251	0.0197	0.0197
	0.0748	0.0746	0.0591	0.0591
o-ClC ₆ H ₄ CH:N.NHCONH ₂	0.0247	0.0247	0.0242	0.0242
	0.0752	0.0750	0.0738	0.0736
(CH ₃) ₂ C:N.NHCONH ₂	0.0142	0.0142	0.0147	0.0147
	0.0433	0.0432	0.0425	0.0424
C ₆ H ₅ CONH.NH ₂	0.0173	0.0173	0.0173	0.0173
	0.0509	0.0508	0.0433	0.0432
(C ₆ H ₅ CH:N) ₂	0.0208	0.0208	0.0207	0.0207
	0.0640	0.0638	0.0667	0.0668
m-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄ CH:N.NHCONH ₂	0.0263	0.0263	0.0257	0.0257
	0.0759	0.0757	0.0762	0.0780
C ₆ H ₅ NHCONH.NH ₂	0.0234	0.0234	..	..
	0.0610	0.0609	..	..
NH ₂ CS.NH.NH ₂	0.0091	0.0091	..	..
	0.0228	0.0228	..	..
o-HO.C ₆ H ₄ CH:N.NHCONH ₂	0.0225	0.0225	..	..
	0.0669	0.0667	..	..
p-CH ₃ OC ₆ H ₄ CH:N.NHCONH ₂	0.0254	0.0254	..	..
	0.0741	0.0739	..	..
C ₆ H ₅ NH.NH ₂ .HCl	0.0181	0.0181	..	..
	0.0447	0.0446	..	..
HCONH.NH.C ₆ H ₅	0.0173	0.0173	..	..
	0.0515	0.0513	..	..

The results recorded above show that the listed reductants can be determined volumetrically by titrating with a standard chloramine-T solution. All chemicals used in this investigation are of guaranteed purity.